

SPECIAL PHYSICAL OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION PREPARATION

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ANNOTATION

The article considers the meaning and features of the organization of professional-applied physical training of students-bachelors, masters, future specialists of various profiles. The main tasks of organizing such training are outlined.

Key words: vocational training, applied training, content, meaning and features of vocational training, computer games, TV viewing, specialization, training tools, learning objectives, further improvement.

OLIIY TA'LIM TALABALARINING MAXSUS JISMONIY TAYYORGARLIK

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada talabalar-bakalavrlar, magistrilar, turli profildagi bo'lajak mutaxassislarning kasbiy-amaliy jismoniy tayyorgarligini tashkil etishning mazmuni va xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqilgan. Bunday mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etishning asosiy vazifalari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kasbiy tayyorgarlik, amaliy mashg'ulotlar, kasbiy tayyorgarlikning mazmuni, mazmuni va xususiyatlari, kompyuter o'yinlari, televizor ko'rish, mutaxassislik, o'qitish vositalari, o'quv maqsadlari, yanada takomillashtirish.

СПЕЦИАЛЬНАЯ ФИЗИЧЕСКАЯ ПОДГОТОВКА СТУДЕНТОВ ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются значение и особенности организации профессионально-прикладной физической подготовки студентов-бакалавров, магистров, будущих специалистов различного профиля. Обозначены основные задачи организации такого обучения.

Ключевые слова: профессиональное обучение, прикладное обучение, содержание, смысл и особенности профессионального обучения, компьютерные игры, просмотр телевизора, специализация, средства обучения, цели обучения, дальнейшее совершенствование.

The public importance of professional-applied physical training of bachelor's, master's students, future specialists of various profiles in modern society is growing every year. This condition is due to the growing trend of a socially dangerous decrease in motor activity.

In the process of mental work, the most typical starting position is the working position sitting at the table. In such a position, repeatedly bent in various joints of the legs, arms, torso and neck, with the head and torso slightly tilted forward - the blood is distributed very unevenly throughout the organs and tissues - adverse congestion may occur in the brain, abdominal cavity, pelvic cavity, and legs.

Many muscle groups in this position experience prolonged and monotonous static tension, especially the muscles of the neck and lower back. As a result of such a long, specifically inclined position of the body, mental workers (economists, accountants, managers) who are not involved in physical education and sports develop shallow breathing, the vital capacity of the lungs decreases, posture is disturbed, the skeletal muscles become decrepit, metabolism decreases. The deteriorating health status of students is of great concern. Scientific and technological progress has led to a change in the conditions of human life. As a result, diseases of civilization have arisen, which

include drug addiction, alcoholism, smoking (especially girls - future mothers), malignant and endocrine diseases, a decrease in functional reserves and resistance to diseases, the birth of weakened offspring.

Students who have spent 6-8 hours at their desks give preference to computer games, watching TV shows, videos and then, and few lead an active healthy lifestyle. The system of market relations requires competitive professionals who have not only special knowledge and skills, but also a high level of efficiency. A professionally trained but not healthy specialist cannot be in demand for a specific activity. In the services of personnel departments, psychologists appear in professional suitability and professional selection, capable of determining the level of compliance and performance, readiness for active work by external signs, physique. The essence of the main tasks solved in the process of professionally applied physical training (PAPT) of students is as follows:

1) to replenish and improve the individual fund of motor skills, skills and physical education knowledge that contribute to the development of the chosen professional activity;

2) to intensify the development of professionally important physical qualities and abilities directly related to them, to ensure the sustainability of the increased level of capacity on this basis;

3) to increase the degree of resistance of the organism in relation to the adverse effects of the environmental conditions in which labor activity takes place, to promote an increase in its adaptive capabilities, the preservation and improvement of health;

4) contribute to the successful fulfillment of common tasks implemented in the system of professional training of personnel, the education of moral, spiritual, strong-willed and other qualities that characterize purposeful, highly active members of society, creating its material and spiritual values.

These tasks in each individual case must be specified in relation to the specifics of the profession and the characteristics of the contingent involved. PAPT can be quite effective only in organic combination with other components of the social system of education as a whole, where the tasks of preparing for educational activities are not reduced to particular immediate tasks characteristic of individual stages of professional and applied training, and are solved not episodically, but permanently. The primary role in their implementation is played by a full-fledged general physical preparation. On the basis of the prerequisites created by it, a specialized PAPT is built.

Its specialization is necessary insofar as it is required by the specificity of professional activity and its conditions, but even in the case of a pronounced specificity, one should not forget about the paramount importance of the principle of all-round assistance to the all-round harmonious development of a person. An

important means of forming professionally important physical qualities and working capacity in universities is physical education, since what kind of specialist a current student will become depends not only on how well he studies, but also on his ability to master healthy life skills.

Realistically and without exaggeration, assessing the current level of students' health, we can say that physical culture in terms of maintaining and improving health should take a much more significant place in the educational and pedagogical process than it does now. Practice shows that in a significant part of university students, the formation of healthy lifestyle skills is chaotic, unorganized.

In higher educational institutions, in physical education classes, the main attention is paid exclusively to improving the level of general physical and sports-technical training of students. Education of the need for physical self-improvement, self-enrichment of the individual, the formation of healthy lifestyle skills with the help of physical and sports activities in practice is most often carried out spontaneously or completely ignored.

Physical education lessons are designed to address the issues of physical education and upbringing, to acquaint the student with the elements of psychophysical training, to take into account the specifics of training and future professional activity, to study the versatile psychological aspects associated with the ability to overcome stressful situations. An important task in the training of specialists is to activate their cognitive activity in the learning process, which means, first of all, to develop their thinking. The conducted observations confirm that university graduates, who were actively involved in physical culture and sports during their studies, successfully navigate in the difficult conditions of enterprises.

However, there are facts that indicate that all the possibilities of physical education are not fully used in solving the problems of preparing students for highly productive work.

At present, PAPT in our country is carried out primarily as one of the sections of the compulsory course of physical education in secondary specialized and higher educational institutions, as well as in the system of scientific organization of labor during the period of the main, professional activity of workers, when this is necessary due to the nature and working conditions.

The need for further improvement and implementation of PAPT in the education system is determined mainly by the following reasons and circumstances:

- 1) the time spent on the development of modern practical professions, and the achievement of professional skills in them continue to depend on the level of functional capabilities of the body, which have a natural basis, on the degree of development of

the physical abilities of the individual, the diversity and perfection of the acquired motor skills and abilities;

2) the productivity of quite a few types of professional labor, despite the progressive decrease in the share of gross muscular efforts in modern material production, directly or indirectly continues to be due to the physical capacity of the performers of labor operations, not only in the field of predominantly physical labor, but also in a number of types of labor activity of a mixed (intellectual-motor) character, like that of machine tool adjusters, assemblers, builders and then; in general, a normal physical condition, without which health and effective functioning are inconceivable, remains the most important prerequisite for a consistently high fruitfulness of any professional work;

3) the problem of preventing the likely negative impacts of certain types of professional labor and its conditions on the physical condition of workers remains; although this problem is solved by many means of optimizing the content and working conditions, including social, scientific, technical and hygienic ones, factors of professionally applied physical culture, including PAPT, are called upon to play an important role among them;

4) promising trends of general social and scientific and technological progress do not relieve a person from the need to constantly improve their activity abilities, and their development due to natural causes is inseparable from the physical improvement of the individual [4].

The essence of the main tasks solved in the PAPT process is to:

1) to replenish and improve the individual fund of motor skills, skills and physical education knowledge that contribute to the development of the chosen professional activity, useful in it and necessary at the same time in the process of PAPT as its means;

2) to intensify the development of professionally important physical abilities and those directly related to them, to ensure the sustainability of an increased level of capacity on this basis;

3) to increase the degree of resistance of the organism in relation to the adverse effects of the environmental conditions in which labor activity takes place, to promote an increase in its adaptive capabilities, the preservation and strengthening of health;

4) contribute to the successful fulfillment of common tasks implemented in the system of professional training of personnel, the education of moral, spiritual, strong-willed and other qualities that characterize purposeful, highly active members of society, creating its material and spiritual values.

These tasks in each individual case must be specified in relation to the specifics of the profession and the characteristics of the contingent involved. However, it is clear that PAPT can be quite effective only in organic combination with other components

of the social system of education as a whole, where the tasks of preparing for work are not reduced to particular immediate tasks characteristic of individual stages of vocational training, and are not solved episodically, but permanently. The paramount role in their implementation, which has already been discussed many times, is played by a full-fledged general physical training. On the basis of the prerequisites created by it, a specialized PAPT is built. Its specialization is necessary insofar as it is required by the specificity of professional activity and its conditions, but even in the case of a pronounced specificity, one should not forget about the paramount importance of the principle of all-round assistance to the all-round harmonious development of a person.

Most researchers indicate that high efficiency in the education of professionally applied physical qualities can be achieved with the help of a wide variety of means of physical culture and sports. At the same time, the special applied exercises used in the process of PAPT are the same ordinary physical exercises, but selected and organized in full accordance with its tasks.

At present, there is no special classification of physical exercises, focused on the tasks of the PAPT of specialists from various professional groups, therefore, in each individual case, this issue should be resolved independently [3].

However, when selecting means of physical education for the purposes of PAPT, it makes sense to conduct a more differentiated grouping of them, which will allow more selective use of these means in the process of physical education of students.

Such groups of means of PAPT students can be considered: applied physical exercises and individual elements from various sports; applied sports; healing forces of nature and hygiene factors; auxiliary means that ensure the rationalization of the educational process in the section PAPT.

Applied physical exercises, and individual elements from various sports, in combination with other exercises, can provide the education of the necessary applied physical and special qualities, as well as the development of applied skills and abilities.

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